

Report on Milestone 36

Case study Roman theatre in Catania: Transfer of the 3D data to the open source Extended Matrix system and concept of a LOD scenario

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Abstract:

We report on the work of Task 5.7 as presented in the SSHOC archaeological case study Workshop – The Roman theatre in Catania from survey to interactive 4D visualization, in May 2021. A focus lies on the concept of a Linked Open Data scenario for the 3D models.

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1. Introduction

This Milestone reports on a snapshot of the work of Task 5.7 (Open Linked Data. Archaeology Case Study), as presented in the SSHOC archaeological case study Workshop – The Roman theatre in Catania from survey to interactive 4D visualization, in May 2021.

In Task 5.7, a virtual reconstruction of the Roman theatre in Catania is being created as an example of an actual transition of archaeological data to the cloud, i.e. from data silos on individual computers to webservices. The case study is based on a unified workflow that starts with the archaeological documentation and results in a virtual reconstruction. With this workflow, data manually acquired during an excavation and traditionally stored on paper can then be stored in the cloud and used for 3D visualisations of the site. The workflow uses tools that are being developed by the task partners, especially the Extended Matrix for 3D reconstruction.

The workflow is accompanied by a Linked Open Data scenario that connects the 3D data with systems for authority data such as gazetteers for place information and ChronOntology for temporal information.

2. Description of the Milestone

The workshop “The Roman theatre in Catania from survey to interactive 4D visualization”, which took place on 25 May 2021, presented the archaeological case study of an actual transition of archaeological survey data from data silos to the cloud that is being developed in Task 5.7. Archaeological field work is a complex process in which scientific resources and competences are allocated for long periods of time, sometimes years. However, the generated data is often either not available in digital form, stuck in data silos or not public. For this reason, the sustainability of archaeological research would benefit immensely from optimized and effective systems of digital documentation, analysis and visualisation of archaeological sites as well as from public, standardised data.

Based on survey data of the Roman theatre in Catania, we showed how the data can be visualized as an interactive virtual reconstruction of the theatre. We also showed how the FAIR principles and semantic

modelling can be applied to archaeological data in practice by standardizing and connecting data and systems from different sources. The absence of public data is also a cultural issue since shareholders are often afraid that the data quality might not be sufficient for publishing.

In the first part of the workshop, we presented the case study as a work in progress. We looked at the data and systems of the three partners, including an existing and a new visualisation of the Roman theatre and the Extended Matrix (EM) system. We concluded the first part with the integration process of systems and data that will lead to a unified workflow from survey data to an interactive 4D visualisation. In the second part we situated the case study in the broader context of the SSHOC project and beyond. Parallel presentations reported on the FAIR principles in archaeology (Holly Wright, ADS), the SSHOC reference ontology SSHOCro (Athina Kritsotaki, FORTH) and the EMViq tool that accompanies the EM system (Bruno Fanini). The workshop ended with a discussion where to go from here and especially how to integrate the FAIR principles and the reference ontology in our work.

Figure 1: The Extended Matrix process

An early version of the Linked Open Data scenario was presented at the Workshop. Since then, the concept has become more concrete. The scenario aims to contextualize the virtual reconstruction of the Roman theatre and make it accessible as Linked Open Data. It connects the Extended Matrix of the Roman theatre with objects, people, places, periods and events that are associated with it, as well as the literature on the Roman theatre. People may have given the order to extend the theatre or carried out the order. Places can mark the area where the theatre is situated or point to other places such as quarries for the building material. Periods may represent the general context of some building activity or the reign of a local ruler. Any building activity is an event. Objects may be part of the structure of the theatre or may have been placed there for ornamental reasons. In addition, the digital objects in the 3D virtualisation have physical counterparts with object types and dimensions.

This creates several new entry points for examining, comparing and searching the 3D model. One can search for concrete objects in the model, but also for object types and object sizes. One can search for

3D models based on the area, the people involved or the time period. If one has found a 3D model, one can search for other models that share connections to norm data such as the area, people, the time period or an event. And one can also search for CIDOC CRM classes, properties and modelling paths as well as the types of the building parts that are used in the EM or its contextualisation.

An example a marble block belonging to an architrave (i.e., a lintel that rests on the capitals of columns), documented in Wilson (1990) and DAI's Arachne database of archaeological objects and part of the EM of the Roman theatre. A drawing of a part of the architrave had already been depicted in volume V of "Le antichità della Sicilia esposte ed illustrate per Domenico Lo Faso Pietrasanta, duca di Serradifalco ... Antichità di Catana", published in 1842 and documented in Arachne and the Heidelberg Digital Library. However, this marble block had fallen in the orchestra of the theatre (the place where the chorus sings and dances) and was only discovered in the 1980s. The block contains an ornamental relief and can be likely dated to the early 3rd century CE. This corresponds to the second major building phase of the Roman theatre during the Severan dynasty (193 to 235), in particular to emperor Elagabalus (218–222) or Alexander Severus (222–235).

This example can be formalized as follows:

Block:

- made of marble
- contains an ornamental relief
- documented in Arachne, based on Wilson
- discovered in the 1980s in the orchestra of the theatre
- which implies that it had fallen down
- part of an architrave
- same dating as the architrave as a whole

Orchestra:

- is a stratigraphic unit in the EM

Architrave:

- is a virtual stratigraphic unit in the EM
- probably early 3rd century CE, according to Wilson
- i.e., likely during the reign of emperor Elagabalus (218–222) or Alexander Severus (222–235)
- which makes it part of the second major building phase of the Roman theatre
- depicted in a book

Second major building phase of the Roman theatre:

- during the Severan dynasty (193 to 235)

documented in the EM

Book:

published in 1842 by the Duca di Serradifalco
documented in Arachne and the Heidelberg Digital Library

2.1. Role of the Milestone

The Milestone documents a snapshot of the work in Task 5.7 as of May 2021. The workshop provided an opportunity to present the work so far, discuss it within SSHOC and among ourselves and to plan out the future work. Due to Covid-19 the task partners have not met in person yet.

2.2. Means of verification

The work has been presented in May 2021 in the SSHOC archaeological case study Workshop – The Roman theatre in Catania from survey to interactive 4D visualization.¹ Additional information on the Linked Open Data scenario is available on GitHub.²

2.3. Explanation on delay in achieving the Milestone

The delay is due to a hiatus between two contracts of the Milestone author.

3. Conclusions and next steps

The work presented at the workshop is the basis for the last year of the project work. Some key problems have been identified, such as copyright issues that prevent the task from making all data available to the

¹ SSHOC archaeological case study Workshop - The Roman theatre in Catania from survey to interactive 4D visualization: <https://sshopencloud.eu/events/sshoc-archaeological-case-study-workshop-roman-theatre-catania-survey-interactive-4d> [accessed May 2021].

² <https://github.com/dainst/sshoc>

public. It helped clarify the scope of the LOD scenario: Examples like the one above need to be expressed with CIDOC CRM and can then be implemented in an RDF triple store.

The CIDOC CRM mappings of the LOD scenario and the EM and their alignment will be reported in Milestone 37. The cooperation with Task 5.6 for implementing the FAIR principles will continue, and the use of the fair principles will be reported Deliverable 5.18, which is the final report on Task 5.7.

4. Appendixes

n/a